

INDICATORS OF SURGICAL REHABILITATION AND QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS WITH INTESTINAL STOMA**Isokulov T.***candidate of medical sciences, head of the Main Medical Office under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan***Mirzaev A.***doctor of medical sciences, Deputy Director for Personnel and Administrative Issues - JSC "NMMC" RU "Kyzylkum"*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13137301>**Abstract**

The article details the history of the development of surgical proctology from the moment colostomy appeared, the imposition of anastomoses, and the stages of surgical treatment of stoma patients. Methods and results of rehabilitation of stoma patients, principles of application and closure of single-double-barreled colostomy, and treatment after surgical complications are discussed. The influence of different methods of surgical treatment on social adaptation and the quality of life of patients is also analyzed.

Keywords: Rehabilitation, surgery, proctology, colostomy, social adaptation, quality of life.

Relevance.

An analysis of world literature and the protocols of many medical institutions shows that the formation of a single-barrel colostomy, both as a preliminary stage and as a final version of surgical intervention, is widely used in the arsenal of surgical treatment of diseases and injuries of the colon and rectum. Many surgical interventions end with colostomy formation in more than 50% of cases, preventively in cases of acute intestinal obstruction complications [1,2,3,4,6,7,8,10,11,12,13].

In emergency cases, when surgery was not planned in advance, colostomy formation often leads to a large number of paracolostomic purulent-inflammatory complications. These complications not only prolong hospitalization periods but also require additional surgical interventions, complicating reconstructive operations and making medical, social, and labor rehabilitation of colostomies patients more difficult, significantly reducing their quality of life and potentially leading to fatal outcomes [9,10,11,12,13].

Modern literature notes that stoma patients often develop an inferiority complex until full recovery. Interaction with others can make patients feel stigmatized, leading to isolation and a persistent sense of hopelessness. This inferiority complex often results from insufficient patient information. Psychological exhaustion can also cause physical weakness and malaise, leading to depression, lifestyle changes, and worsened social adaptation, all of which affect quality of life. Psychological support significantly improves social adaptation and quality of life [5].

Among modern surgeons, there are two competing methods: manual techniques for colorectal anastomoses and device-assisted anastomosis formation [10,16].

Proctologists must be familiar with both methods as each patient requires an individualized approach. Currently, quality of life (QoL) is an important, and in

some situations, a primary criterion for assessing treatment effectiveness in clinical studies [10,14,15].

QoL reflects the impact of the disease and treatment on patient well-being and characterizes their physical, emotional, and social well-being, which changes under the influence of the disease or its treatment.

Objective: To improve surgical rehabilitation outcomes by optimizing reconstructive operations and studying the quality of life, dynamics in patients with intestinal stomas.

Materials and methods We analyzed the results of observations of 397 patients with intestinal stomas from 2012-2019, who were hospitalized at the Republican Clinical Hospital No. 1 of Uzbekistan. All patients underwent standard examination, including clinical examination and instrumental methods: ECG, ultrasound, radiography, esophagogastroduodenoscopy, fibrocolonoscopy, rectosigmoidoscopy, digital sphincterometry, proctography, irrigography, colonoscopy, diagnostic laparoscopy, and pouch-grahy as necessary.

To exclude abdominal neoplasms and identify other pathologies, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and multislice computed tomography (MSCT) with contrast were used as needed. Quality of life was assessed using the European Quality of Life Questionnaire EuroQol-5D and the visual analog scale (VAS) for pain intensity, validated through standard procedures. After diagnosis, all patients underwent surgical intervention—colostomy formation, various anastomoses, and other reconstructive operations.

Results and Discussions. In total, 397 patients with intestinal stomas were studied from 2012-2019. Patients were distributed by age according to WHO classification. The majority were young (18-44 years; 74%), with men predominating over women by 10% (Table 1).

Table 1

Age (years)	Gender				Number of patients	
	Men		Women			
	aбс.	%	aбс.	%	aбс.	%
18-44*	160	54,79	132	45,21	292	73,55
45-59	47	60,26	31	39,74	78	19,65
60-74	14	56,00	11	44,00	25	6,30
75-90	2	100,00	0	0,00	2	0,50
Bcero	223	56,17	174	43,83	397	100,00

Note: *16 years – 2 males and 1 female. 17 years – 1 male. No patients older than 90 years were observed in our study.

Patients aged 18-44 comprised 73% of the total, with men constituting 55% and women 45%, attributed to lifestyle factors affecting intestinal function. The analysis showed that diseases mainly affected the working-age population (18-59 years; ~93%), highlighting the importance of this issue.

In our study, in 397 patients, the reasons for ostomy placement were as follows: nonspecific ulcerative colitis 140 (35.3%), intestinal bleeding for various reasons 98 (24.7%), intestinal stricture 30 (7.6%), purulent-inflammatory diseases. intestines and peritonitis

19 (4.8%), ulcerative proctitis 19 (4.8%), abdominal pain syndrome 15 (3.8%), adhesive intestinal disease 14 (3.5%), colon diverticulosis 12 (3 %), Crohn's disease 11 (2.5%), ulcerative proctitis 10 (2.5%), volvulus 9 (2.3%), Hirschsprung's disease 5 (1.3%), abdominal trauma 3, duodenal ulcer intestines with perforation 3 and intestinal amebiasis 2 cases, depending on the cause, various stomas or surgical methods were used (Table 2).

Table 2

Nosologically forms of diseases for which ileostomy or colostomy were performed (n= 397)

№	Nosologically form	Quantity	%
1	Nonspecific ulcerative colitis	140	35.3
2	Amebiasis of the colon	2	0.5
3	Volvulus of the sigmoid colon	9	2.3
4	Abdominal injury	3	0.8
5	Diverticulosis of the colon	12	3.0
6	Crohn's disease	11	2.8
7	Diffuse polyposis of the colon	3	0.8
8	Hirschsprung's disease	5	1.3
9	Intestinal bleeding	98	24.7
10	Intestinal stricture	30	7.6
11	Ulcerative proctitis	10	2.5
12	Peritonitis, purulent-inflammatory diseases	19	4.8
13	Duodenal ulcer	3	0.8
14	Intestinal obstruction	19	4.8
15	Adhesive bowel disease	14	3.5
16	Abdominal pain syndrome	15	3.8
17	Uterine fibroids	4	1.0
Total:		397	100%

Based on the severity of the disease, patients were divided into three groups. The first group included 131 (33%) newly admitted patients who underwent colostomy, anastomosis, and other surgical interventions, assessed as having a milder disease course. The second

group consisted of 133 (33.5%) patients who had undergone various surgical interventions previously, with moderate disease severity. The third group included 133 (33.5%) patients with severe disease, who had undergone multiple surgeries and continued to have recurrent issues (Table 3).

Table 3

Distribution of patients by group (n=397)

Groups	Number of Patients	%
1	131	33,0
2	133	33,5
3	133	33,5
Total	397	100

Analysis of the treatment types in 397 patients showed the following results: In the first group, anastomosis was the most common procedure (78, 60%); followed by double-barrel stoma (35, 27%); single-barrel

stoma (8, 6%); reconstructive surgeries (6, 5%); and conservative treatment (4, 3%). Anastomosis is the preferred surgical method in this group for faster recovery (Table 4).

Table 4

Treatment types in the first group (n=131)

	Treatment Methods	Number (abs.)	%
1.	Single-barreled stoma application	8	6,1
2.	Double-barreled stoma application	35	26,7
3.	Anastomosis application	78	59,5
4.	Reconstructive surgeries	6	4,6
5.	Conservative treatment	4	3,1
	Total:	131	100

In the second group, the most common procedures were: closure of double-barrel stoma (35, 26%); anastomosis (28, 21%); closure of single-barrel stoma (15, 11%); reconstructive surgeries (15, 11%); and conservative treatment (40, 30%). Anastomosis was less

common in this group compared to the first, but remained a method of choice. Many patients (30%) received conservative treatment and rehabilitation (Table 5).

Table 5

Treatment types in the second group (n=133)

	Treatment Methods	Number (abs.)	%
1.	Single-barreled stoma closure	15	11,3
2.	Double-barreled stoma closure	35	26,3
3.	Anastomosis application	28	21,1
4.	Reconstructive surgeries	15	11,3
5.	Conservative treatment	40	30,1
	Total:	133	100

In the third group, the most common procedures were: closure of double-barrel stoma (38, 29%); closure of single-barrel stoma (26, 19%); anastomosis (24, 18%); reconstructive surgeries (15, 11%); and conservative treatment (30, 23%). Anastomosis was performed less frequently in this group compared to the

first and second groups, but remained a preferred method of surgical treatment. Conservative treatment was provided to 22% of patients who continued to suffer and required rehabilitation (Table 6).

Table 6

Treatment types in the third group (n=133)

	Treatment Methods	Number (abs.)	%
1.	Single-barreled stoma closure	26	19,5
2.	Double-barreled stoma closure	38	28,6
3.	Anastomosis application	24	18,0
4.	Reconstructive surgeries	15	11,3
5.	Conservative treatment	30	22,6
	Total:	133	100

Among the 397 patients, 74 (18%) received conservative treatment. In the first group, 4 (3%) patients required conservative treatment after surgery due to signs of intestinal obstruction, which resolved without additional surgical intervention. In the second group, 40 (30%) patients who had previously undergone surgery required conservative treatment, which resolved

signs of dynamic intestinal obstruction without further surgery. In the third group, 30 (23%) patients with a history of multiple surgeries required conservative treatment to resolve signs of dynamic intestinal obstruction (Table 7).

Table 7

Patients receiving conservative treatment (n=397)					
Groups	Number of Patients	%	Number (abs.)	%	Total Patients in Group (%)
1	131	33,0	4	5,4	3,1
2	133	33,5	40	54,1	30,1
3	133	33,5	30	40,5	22,6
Total:	397	100	74	100	18,6

Conclusion

Thus, 93% of the patients were aged 18-59 years, with men comprising 55% and women 45%, highlighting the issue as it predominantly affects the working-age population. Among the 397 patients, 165 (42%) had comorbidities, which significantly impacted their quality of life and slowed recovery after treatment and rehabilitation. The most common surgical treatment was anastomosis (130, 40%) in all groups, followed by the formation and closure of double-barrel stoma (108, 33%) and single-barrel stoma (49, 15%). Reconstructive surgeries (36, 11%) were less common. The analysis showed varying degrees of quality of life, deterioration across the three groups, with the first group's quality of life being closest to normal, the second group experiencing moderate deterioration, and the third group having significant deterioration that recovered slowly. Emotional state significantly impacted parameters like pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression in the EuroQol-5D questionnaire.

References

1. Analysis of observations showed that, the disease of patients comes mainly at the working age of 18-59 years about 93% which makes the problem very urgent.
2. The predominant method of surgical treatment is the application of anastomoses 130 (40%) in all studied groups, the ratio to the total number of patients 33%, in the second place the application and closure of bipolar stoma 108 (33%) out of a total of 27%.
3. A study of 397 patients showed that the most affected parameters of PC pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression were the emotional state of the patients.
4. The visual-analogue scale and its five parameters allow more detailed examination of pain syndrome, absence of pain (0 points), weak pain (1-3 points), moderate pain (4-6 points), very severe pain (7-9 points), unbearable pain (10 points) which means the maximum possible feeling of pain.

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